

A Women in Crop Science Conversation with..... Aparna Das

Julie Van Vlasselaer¹

¹International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center (CIMMYT), Texcoco, Mexico

Contact: j.vanvlasselaer@cgiar.org

Background

We continue our Women in Crop Science conversation with one of the nicest individuals I know. I had the pleasure to ask some questions to Aparna Das, Technical Program Manager for the Global Maize Program at CIMMYT (International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center). But maybe more interesting, convener of the WIRES (Women in Research and Science; <https://gdi.cgiar.org/erg-hub/wires/>) organizing group. WIRES is a vibrant new voluntary employee resource group that's dedicated to championing and supporting women within the CGIAR.

You can find out more about Aparna's work here: <https://www.cimmyt.org/people/aparna-das/>

A Women in Crop Science conversation

Briefly describe what you do?

I am a plant breeder, trained for incorporating modern technologies into breeding programs to fast-track the product development and deployment timelines. Presently I am the Technical Program Manager for the Global Maize Program at CIMMYT, based in Nairobi, Kenya. I work with breeding and the allied teams to implement new strategies to improve the breeding product delivery pipeline.

Why did you get into research and especially Crop Science?

My interest in science, especially the biological sciences was the baseline for my moving into to crop sciences. My education in one of the finest Agricultural Universities in India (Punjab Agriculture University) was the major influence for my moving into the field of crop science. The effect of the 'green revolution' on the farming community in the region (Punjab, India) in which I was brought up was as an add-on influence for me to continue to advance my career in this field as I could see how the products from research changed the agriculture scenario in the region which ultimately improved the society standards in general and especially the farming community.

Lab or field? Field

Conference or stakeholder meeting? Stakeholder meeting

Literature review or project report? Project report

Conventional or molecular methods? Molecular method combined with conventional.

Hybrid, inbred or vegetative? ALL!

Qualitative or quantitative research? Both!

GenStat or R? R

Favourite crop & why?

I am a breeder who has worked in multiple crops (rice, potato, vegetables, wheat, corn), all crops are like my children, difficult to name a favourite child 😊.

What do you love the most about your job?

The development of products critical for food security for future.

Any major hurdles?

Minor hurdles only.

What is your dream to achieve in your field of expertise?

Making products available to the farming community.

Who has influenced you the most and why?

'My father' in my early years who guided me to always stand up for 'right' and believe in myself. Multiple leaders in my career, especially Michel Ragot, my line manager at Syngenta who showed what team building and leadership is about and how leaders can influence both individual and team performance.

Most important publication or the publication of which you are most proud?

My first publication from my master's research!

'Cytogenetic studies of male sterile mutants of wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) to identify apomictic development'

I am especially proud of this work because I worked on lab techniques combined with intensive fieldwork! This encouraged and motivated me to combine technology with fieldwork for the identification of an impactful product.

*Unfortunately, the online version of the publication is not available, but here are some links to other publications from Aparna's PhD work:

<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1023/A:1003965724880>

<https://agris.fao.org/agris-search/search.do?recordID=IN2022019405>

What is your favourite aspect of your research?

Understanding crops and how they respond to different treatments and/or conditions.

What would make your research and crop science experience even better?

Unbiased performance evaluations (Crop & People).

What is the best career decision you ever made and why?

To always make efforts to learn new things and evolve professionally.

Where do you see yourself in 5 years?

Wherever my hard work, passion & destiny takes me.

Beach or mountain? Mountain

Tea or coffee? Tea

Appetizer or dessert? Appetizer

Instagram or Twitter? None!

Fame or fortune? Both, but combined with contentment.

Final word

Aparna and I moved to Nairobi, Kenya around the same time, September 2018. Although I was not working for CIMMYT around that time, we connected as newbies in a completely new town right away. Aparna always has a clear view on things, on personal issues as well as professional. When you need advice, she will be able to give you her unbiased opinion; even if it is something you don't want to hear. That's something valuable and something I really appreciate! Thank you very much Aparna for taking your time and just of the record, when can I come over to have Indian food again?